

Access and use of e-resources among Youth Extension Agents in Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined Access to and use of e-resources among youth extension agents in Katsina State, Nigeria. A two-stage sampling procedure was employed to choose 74 youth extension agents. The collection of primary data through a well-organized questionnaire and descriptive statistics were used for the analysis. The results revealed that the extension agents had a mean age of 37 years with 52% aged between 38-40 years. The majority (90.5%) of the extension agents were male, married (90.5%), whereas 45.9% had between 1 and 10 years of working experience. The majority of those who responded had access to E-library ($\bar{x} = 2.72$), E-video conferencing ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), E-commerce ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), online databases ($\bar{x} = 2.46$), E-marketing ($\bar{x} = 2.42$), E-journal ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), E-agriculture ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), and E-magazine ($\bar{x} = 2.26$), while E-video conferencing, E-library, E-commerce, online data base, E-journal, E-magazine, E-marketing and E-agriculture were considered most utilized E-resources. High cost of subscription ($\bar{x} = 2.20$), low literacy level of extension agents ($\bar{x} = 2.03$) and internet connectivity distance from the office ($\bar{x} = 1.92$) were the major constraints to use of e-resources tools. The research comes to the conclusion that E-video conferencing, E-library, E-commerce, online data base, E-journal, E-magazine, E-marketing and E-agriculture were the easiest to access and regularly utilize tools in the area of study. It recommends that other development organizations and the Government ought to offer internet access to extension workers and also give the extension agents' frequent training on the application of E-resources.

Keywords: E-Resource access, Extension-Agents, E-agriculture

INTRODUCTION

The delivery of agricultural extension services is always evolving due to the worldwide developments in the field of information and communication technology (ICT). ICT has enormous ability to revitalize the delivery of dormant agricultural extension services (Fawole et al., 2024). With the development of ICT and its accessories, farmers are now only a click away from extension agents and the information that can promptly address their concerns. Previously, farmers had to wait months or even forever to obtain technical information and/or extension agents (Mutimba, 2024). These days, e-resources are widely used worldwide for both official and personal purposes by people, businesses, and intergovernmental organizations (Humbhi et al., 2023). All human endeavors, including medicine, education, library science, architecture, and agriculture, have benefited from its use. Systems for gathering weather data, market data, monitoring of pests and insects, databases of agricultural information, e-agriculture, the internet, and other applications are frequently utilized in the agricultural industry to support the provision of extension services, as reported by (Humbhi et al., 2023). ICT advancements in Africa are creating new avenues for African farmers to expand their knowledge base and improve their quality of life (Fawole et al., 2018; Ayim et al. 2022). Globally, the provision of agricultural extension services has focused on informing farmers about research findings and ways to enhance

agricultural practices. The primary source of agricultural information in Nigeria is research institutes that develop new technology that are then distributed to farmers via extension programs. Therefore, the Center for Agricultural Research Information Services is responsible for maintaining a number of information resources, including farmers' magazines, radio, television, movies, handbooks, posters, newspapers, and mobile telecommunication systems, as well as providers of agricultural information, including non-governmental organizations, international organizations, and community-based (Moruppa & Ijabula, 2021).

Electronic resources, or "e-resources," are any materials that need to be accessed through a computer (ICT devices), be it a personal computer or a portable mobile device (Felix, 2024), and can be viewed locally or remotely over a network. According to Yarima and Saidu (2020), the usage of e-resources through actual carriers (such as discs, flash drives, cassettes, and cartridges) intended to be inserted into a computer or the equipment that goes with it is known as "direct access to electronic resources." Nevertheless, no physical carrier can be used for remote access. E-journals, databases, e-books, and reference databases (encyclopedias, directories, biographies), electronic images and audio/visual materials, etc. can all be accessed through a terminal or other input-output device that is linked to a computer (such as a resource network). The internet, online databases, electronic

products, online libraries, and collections that may be clicked, and other online materials are examples of e-resources.

Any electronic product (E-resources) that offers a collection of data as a published, commercially available title, including text, full-text databases, electronic journals, image collections, and other multimedia goods, as well as numerical, graphical, or time-based data with the intention of being marketed, requires computer access (Shehu, 2023). E-resources offer users the convenience of time and location, the capability of text search immediately, the opportunity to connect and access additional reading content, and the capacity to spread and disseminate information (Patil & Mulimani, 2025).

Nwabukwu et al. (2019) E-agricultural extension, according to the report, is a method that allows extension agents to contact farmers through more effective alternatives to a conventional agricultural system that make use of mobile web, downloaded apps, SMS, Interactive Voice Response (IVR), and Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD). Because the target consumers have a wide variety of mobile devices, most services would be copied across multiple technologies to serve a bigger clientele. This boosts profitability, efficiency as well as competitiveness internationally. The introduction of manpower, fertilizers, chemicals, better seeds, and improved agricultural techniques and methods, the impact of technology on agriculture has been demonstrated over time. Farmers may find it easier to obtain market data, land services and resources, disease and pest control, and rural development initiatives with the introduction of numerous relevant online resources for agricultural data transmission (Abiri et al., 2023).

E-resources make it easier to gather, process, store, and share information (Olubiyo & Olubiyo, 2023). The degree of interactivity varies among e-resources; radio, telephone, and television are examples of classic e-resources that are less interactive. Adedokun and Fawole (2018) find more interactive electronic resources, including computers, smartphones, and the internet. They can be referred to as modern ICTs and enable more collaboration. Because agricultural research institutes are remote from farms, electronic resources play a crucial function in connecting agricultural research with the extension system (Khan et al., 2024).

Vikas et al. (2020) found that the majority of research institutes for agriculture have the fundamental ICT resources required to handle as well as spread data

resulting from research activities. Makinde et al. (2025) defines e-resources as those that let farmers, extension agents, and researchers communicate with each other. These technologies improve the timely availability of information required for making decisions. Agricultural researchers benefit from ICTs because they make it easier to obtain the data they need to conduct their research. The tools can be used by agricultural extension workers to get information from various sources, including research institutes, and to convey practical problems to research institutes. Agricultural stakeholders can make logical judgments thanks to the ease with which e-resources can be accessed and utilized.

Agricultural extension agents must stay current with knowledge and advancements in their fields of expertise. This is due to their active involvement in enhancing plant and animal species, technology, and maintaining best practices required to reach agricultural production targets. With the introduction of the internet, which is a network of networks, there has been a paradigm shift in how individuals network and collaborate.

Despite the fact that many professionals use email, few studies have been able to offer actual data on the use of e-resources by extension agents in Katsina State and the reasons for their use. Therefore, this study assessed the use of e-resources among youth extension agents in Katsina State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the youth extension agents in the study area.
2. examine the level of access to e-resources among youth extension agents.
3. ascertain the frequency of e-resources usage among the youth extension agents.
4. identify the constraints to the use of e-resources among youth extension agents.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Katsina State, which is situated in Nigeria's North-Western geopolitical zone. The state's borders are as follows: Zamfara State to the west, Kaduna State to the south, Jigawa and Kano States to the east, and Niger Republic to the north. Situated between latitudes 12°15'N and longitudes 7°30'E, it has a land area of 24,192 square kilometers. Three agro-ecological zones comprise Katsina State: the Northern Guinea savannah, the Sudan savannah, and the Sahel savannah. The region has a semi-arid environment with an average annual rainfall of roughly 689 millimeters, mostly from May to

September. Among the state's principal crops are vegetables, sorghum, millet, cotton, groundnuts, cowpeas, and maize.

The study's respondents were chosen using a two-stage sampling process. Funtua and Dutsin-Ma Agricultural Zones were purposefully chosen for the first stage because, out of the three ADP Zones in Katsina State, they have the most extension agents due to their more intensive agricultural activity. A proportionate random selection of extension agents from the two zones is

made in the second stage. As a result, thirty-six (36) respondents from zones II (Funtua) and thirty-eight (38) respondents from zones III (Dutsin-Ma) of KTARDA were chosen for the study, totaling seventy-four (74) respondents.

$$\text{Proportionate Sampling } S = \frac{n}{N} X$$

n = Number of Extension Agents in each zone

N = Total no of extension in the two zones

S = Sample Size (desired)

X = Sampling size

Table 1: Summary of the Sample Design Outlay

S/N	(KTARDA) Zones	Sample Frame	Sample Size
1	Zone II (Funtua)	39	36
2	Zone III (Dutsin-Ma)	44	38
Total		83	74

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Extension Agents

The result in Table 2 revealed that most (52.7%) of those surveyed ranged from 38-40 years of age, whereas just 10.8% of the studied population fell into the lowest age group of 29–32 years. 37 years old was the responders' average age. This implies that the majority of extension workers in the research area are young, active people in the productive age group, which may enhance their use of innovations in the delivery of extension services, including e-resources. The outcome is consistent with the findings of Fawole et al. (2016), who reported that most extension agents in Katsina State were young, active people between the ages of 44. The findings are also consistent with those of Thomas and Laseinde (2015), who reported that none of the agricultural extension agents in Oyo State, Nigeria, are younger than 20 and that most of them are between the ages of 41 and 50. In a similar vein, Yakubu et al. (2013) found that most extension agents between the ages of 41 and 50 were middle-aged (48.8%), indicating that they were capable of making decisions on the use of ICTs.

Additionally, Table 2 statistics revealed that 90.5% of the extension agents were men and only 9.5% were women. This suggests that the number of male extension agents in the research area was higher. Of the respondents, the majority (90.5%) were married, 4.1% were single, and only 5.4% were divorced. These findings suggested that married people made up the majority of respondents. This result is consistent with that of Banmeke et al. (2020), who stated that majority (74.5 %) of the sampled agricultural extension agents were males. Similarly, Inuwa et al. (2024) also

observed that field-level agricultural extension work was dominated by men. Gender equality in agricultural extension work is negatively impacted by men's dominance in the field. According to Table 2, the respondents' educational backgrounds ranged from a diploma to a master. Of these, 48.7% had an OND or NCE as their highest qualification, 33.8% an HND, 10.8% a B.Sc., and 6.7% an M.Sc. These results are consistent with those of Idiakke-Ochei et al. (2016), who studied the information-seeking practices of extension workers in Edo State, Nigeria, where the majority of respondents (52.6%) had OND/NCE as their primary qualification and were literate. This suggests that all of the respondents had some sort of educational background. Additionally, it implies that they have the fundamental educational background required to comprehend the intricacies of e-resource tools, which raises the possibility that they can manage and employ them successfully for specialized tasks like sharing agricultural information. The bulk of respondents (60.8%) earned between N50,000 and N100,000 per month (60.81), followed by those who earned less than N50,000 (29.7%) and those who made between N100,000 and N150,000 (9.5%). This meant that the extension agents had an average salary, so they might have the resources to buy and use e-materials. Seven people made up the average household. This indicates that the households of the extension workers in the area were quite substantial.

The majority of extension workers (41.9%) had worked for 11–20 years, whereas 1.4% had worked for 31–40 years, according to the results shown in Table 2. The extension agents have an average of 15 years of professional experience. As shown in the table, out of the 74 respondents, (79.7%) were computer literate while (20.3%) were not computer literate and also,

majority (90.5%) of the respondent had access to e-resources while a few numbers (9.5%) do not have access to e-resources tools.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents According to Socio-economic Characteristics (n=74)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age (Years)			
29-31	8	10.81	
32-34	5	6.76	
35-37	22	29.73	
38-40	39	52.70	36.59
Sex			
Male	67	90.54	
Female	7	9.46	
Marital status			
Single	3	4.05	
Married	67	90.54	
Divorced	4	5.41	
Household size			
1-5	27	36.20	
6-10	35	47.30	7.01
11-15	8	10.81	
16-20	4	5.41	
Educational level			
OND/NCE	36	48.65	
HND	25	33.78	
B.SC	8	10.81	
M.SC	5	6.76	
Working experience			
1-10	26	35.14	
11-20	31	41.89	15.09
21-30	16	21.62	
31-40	1	1.35	
Monthly income (₦)			
<50,000	22	29.73	
50,000-100,000	45	60.81	
100,001-150,000	7	9.46	
Computer literacy			
Yes	59	79.7	
No	15	20.3	
Access to e-resources tools			
Yes	67	90.50	
No	7	9.50	
Total	74	100	

Source: Field Survey, (2021)

Level of access to e-resources tools by the extension agents

Table 3 below shows the outcome of the extension agents' access to e-resources. The findings showed that the highest level of E-resources accessible to extension agents in the study area was on E-library ($\bar{x} = 2.72$), followed by E-video conferencing with the mean score of 1.49, E-commerce ranked third with the mean score of ($\bar{x} = 2.65$), online databases ranked fourth with the mean score of ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), E-marketing ranked fifth

with the mean score of ($\bar{x} = 2.46$). The next in the ranking, was e-journal. This had mean scores of ($\bar{x} = 2.42$) and ranked sixth, followed by E-journal and e-agriculture with the mean score of ($\bar{x} = 2.41$) respectively, E-magazine ($\bar{x} = 2.26$), U-tube ($\bar{x} = 2.00$), Twitter ($\bar{x} = 1.89$), E-radio ($\bar{x} = 1.57$), Email ($\bar{x} = 1.54$), Facebook ($\bar{x} = 1.51$), while the least level of access to e-resources among the respondents was on WhatsApp ($\bar{x} = 1.45$). These results indicated that E-library, E-video conferencing, E-commerce,

online databases, E –marketing, E-journal and E-agriculture were the most accessible tools in the study area. This might be a result of the extent to which the

extension agents in the research area have access to e-resources.

Table 3: Distribution of respondent by level of access to the e-resources tools

E-resources tools	Always	Occasionally	Rarely	Mean	SD
E-library	4(5.4)	14(18.9)	56(75.7)	2.72	.586
E-video conferencing	4(5.4)	19(25.7)	51(68.9)	2.65	.607
E-commerce	8(10.8)	18(24.3)	48(64.9)	2.55	.705
Online databases	11(14.9)	19(25.7)	44(59.5)	2.46	.762
E -marketing	14(18.9)	16(21.6)	44(59.5)	2.42	.811
E- journal	12(16.2)	20(27.0)	42(56.8)	2.41	.757
E -agriculture	15(20.3)	15(20.3)	44(59.5)	2.41	.826
E-magazine	17(23.0)	22(29.7)	35(47.3)	2.26	.829
U-tube	31(41.9)	13(17.6)	30(40.5)	2.00	.936
Twitter	38(51.4)	9(12.2)	27(36.5)	1.89	.987
E-radio	45(60.8)	16(21.6)	13(17.6)	1.57	.778
Email	43(58.1)	23(31.1)	8(10.8)	1.54	.725
Facebook	53(71.6)	5(6.8)	16(21.6)	1.51	.864
WhatsApp	55(74.3)	6(8.1)	13(17.6)	1.45	.813

Source: Field Survey, (2021); Figures in Parentheses are in Percentages

Frequency of E-resources Tools Usage among Extension Agents

The distribution of extension agents based on the frequency of e-resource utilization is displayed in Table 4. The e-resources tools usage among extension agents were ranked in order of frequency using the mean score. The results showed that E-video conferencing was ranked 1st with a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.66). This ranking showed that e-video conferencing could help the extension agents in providing farmers with information. E-library was ranked 2nd (\bar{x} =3.61). This suggests that extension agents' usage of e-libraries is very beneficial for providing farmers with knowledge. If this E-resource is adequately handled, the frequency of usage will be of great benefit to the farmers. E-commerce was the 3rd most frequently used E-resources in the area

(\bar{x} =3.47). Online data base and E-journal were the 4th most frequently used E-resources in the study area (\bar{x} =3.41) respectively. Followed by E-magazine (\bar{x} =3.31), E-marketing (\bar{x} =2.96), E-agriculture (\bar{x} =2.91), U-tube (\bar{x} =2.49), Twitter (\bar{x} =2.36), Email (\bar{x} =2.16), E-radio (\bar{x} =2.15), Facebook (\bar{x} =1.86) and WhatsApp (\bar{x} =1.77). These results indicated that e-video conferencing, e-library, e-commerce, online data base, e-journal, e-magazine, e-marketing and e-agriculture were the most frequently used tools in the study area. This could be because the research area's extension agents have access to a limited number of e-resource tools. The findings corroborate that of Nwabugwu et al. (2019) which demonstrated the utilization of e-resources by extension personnel was generally low in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Distribution of respondent by frequency of use of E-resources

E-resource tool	Daily	Twice/weekly	Weekly	Never	Mean	Ranking
E- video conferencing	3	3	10	58	3.66	1 st
E-library	4	5	7	58	3.61	2 nd
E-commerce	3	10	10	51	3.47	3 rd
Online databases	7	7	9	51	3.41	4 th
E-journal	9	6	8	51	3.41	5 th
E-magazine	9	6	12	47	3.31	6 th
E-marketing	14	12	11	37	2.96	7 th
E-agriculture	16	12	9	37	2.91	8 th
U-tube	25	13	11	25	2.49	9 th
Twitter	33	9	3	29	2.38	10 th
E-mail	30	12	22	10	2.16	11 th
E-radio	36	8	13	17	2.15	12 th
Facebook	47	8	1	18	1.86	13 th
WhatsApp	51	5	2	16	1.77	14 th

Source: Field Survey, (2021).

Constraints to the use of E-resources tools.

Several limitations related to the usage of e-resources are displayed in Table 5. The constraints identified by the extension agents were ranked in order of agreement using the mean score. According to the table, limitations include: high cost of subscription ($\bar{x}=2.20$), low literacy level of extension agents ($\bar{x}=2.03$), distance of internet connectivity from office ($\bar{x}=1.92$), high cost of e-resources facilities ($\bar{x}=1.86$), very limited access ($\bar{x}=1.82$), lack of money to access the e-resources ($\bar{x}=1.58$), lack of technical expertise necessary for the e-resources ($\bar{x}=1.55$), lack of skills in e-resources usage ($\bar{x}=1.50$), lack of awareness/knowledge on e-

resources ($\bar{x}=1.49$) and unstable electric power supply ($\bar{x}=1.39$). This result indicates that the primary limitations related to the utilization of electronic resources in the research area are high subscription costs, extension agents' low literacy levels, the distance between the office and the internet, and the expensive cost of e-resource facilities. This is also in line with the findings of Nwabugwu et al. (2019), who listed a number of issues, including extension staff members' ignorance of e-resources, the difficulty of using them, their unavailability, poor internet connectivity, and the expensive cost of internet access.

Table 5: Distribution of respondent by constraints to the use of e-resources tools

Constraints	SA	A	ND	D	SD	Mean	SD
High cost of subscription	30	19	9	12	4	2.20	1.282
Unstable electric power supply	27	30	7	8	2	2.03	1.072
Distance of internet connectivity from office	28	34	5	4	3	1.92	1.017
High cost of E-resources facilities	28	36	4	4	2	1.86	.941
Very limited access	27	38	6	1	2	1.82	.850
Lack of money to access the e-resources	42	25	4	2	1	1.58	.828
Lack of technical expertise necessary for the e-resources	43	23	7	-	1	1.55	.779
Lack of skills in e-resources usage	47	23	1	-	3	1.50	.880
Lack of awareness/knowledge on E-resources	45	25	2	1	1	1.49	.745
Low literacy level of extension agents	50	20	3	1	-	1.39	.637

Source: Field Survey, (2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that e-video conferencing, e-library, e-commerce, online databases, e-journal, e-magazine, e-marketing, and e-agriculture were found to be the most widely available and commonly utilized tools in

the study area. Furthermore, the results showed that the main obstacles to the use of e-resources tools were a lack of proficiency in using e-resources, low literacy among extension agents, the distance between the office and internet connectivity, the high cost of e-

resources facilities, and extremely restricted access to e-resources.

According to the study's recommendation, the government and other development organizations should give extension workers access to the internet and the necessary e-resources tools, such as online

databases, e-marketing, and e-journals. They should also give regular e-resource training top priority. To enhance their skills and elevate their literacy level, extension agents should receive timely and continuous training on how to use e-resources.s

REFERENCES

- Abiria, R., Rizanb, N., Balasundramb, S.K., Shahbazic, A.B. & Abdul-Hamida, H. (2023). Application of digital technologies for ensuring agricultural productivity. *Heliyon Journal*, 9, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e22601>
- Adedokun, T. O. & Fawole, O. (2018). Use of Electronic Information Resources by Undergraduates of National Open University of Nigeria in Ilorin Study Center. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 11(1), 116-124.
- Aliyu, A. A. & Umar, S. (2019). Socio-economic factors influencing extension workers' satisfaction with job condition in Kebbi State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KARKA), Kebbi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development Studies*, 6(4), 1-6.
- Ayim, C., Kassahun, A., Addison, C. & Tekinerdogan, B. (2022). Adoption of ICT innovations in the agriculture sector in Africa: a review of the literature. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 11(22), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40066-022-00364-7>
- Banmeke, T. O. A., Akwamuzor, B. O. & Kareem, R. F. (2020). Public Agricultural Extension Agents' Knowledge of the Concept of Eextension in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Rural Sociology*, 20(2), 46-51.
- Bhukuvhani, C., Chiparausha, B. & Zuvalinyenga, D. (2012). Effects of electronic information resources skills training for lecturers on pedagogical practices and research productivity, *International Journal of Education and Development*, 8(1), 16-28.
- Fawole, B.E., Akinyemi, M. & Sanusi, W.A. (2016). Accessibility and relevance of information communication technology in extension delivery to rural farming households in Katsina State, Nigeria. In I.N. Nwachukwu, C.O. Amadi, J.E. Ewuziem, B.C. Okoye, S.O. Afuape, N.M. Agwu & O.U. Oteh (Eds.), *Economic diversification: The agricultural road map* (pp. 912-915). Agricultural Society of Nigeria (ASN).
- Fawole, B.E., Garba, H. S. & Ebenehi O. (2024). Factors Influencing Usage of Information and Communication Technologies among Maize Farmers in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (NJAAT)*. 4(2), 68-76.
- Fawole, B.E., Garba, H.S., Olatinwo, L.K. and Adisa, R.S. (2018). Analysis of Use of Information and Communication Technologies among Maize Farmers in Zaria Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology*, 4(1) 124-130.
- Fawole, O.P. & Olajide B.R. (2012). Awareness and use of information communication technologies by farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information*, 13(4), 326-337.
- Felix, T.O. (2024). Electronic Information Resources Usage in Public and Private Universities. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 12(3), 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.14662/ijalis2024200>
- Humbhi, S., Tareen, S., Raheem, A., & Humbhi, A. (2023). Awareness and Utilization of E-Resources to Support Academic and Research Activities. *IAFOR Journal of Literature & Librarianship*, 12(2), 107-129.
- Iidiaka-Ochei, O., Onemolease E. A. & Erie, G. O. (2016). Information seeking behaviour of extension personnel in Edo State, Nigeria. *Scholar's Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences. Veterinary Science*, 3(4), 318-319.
- Igbo, U. H., & Imo, N. T. (2010). Challenges of accessibility of information

- resources by the post graduate library users of a Nigeria University. *An International Journal of Information and Communication Technology*, 7(2), 1-10.
- Inuwa, M. P., Murtala, N. & Garba, M. (2024). Extension Workers Utilization of E-Extension in Dissemination of Agricultural Technology in Gombe State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (NJAAT)*, 4(1), 2811-1885.
- Khan, R. P., Gupta, S., Daum, T., Birner, R., & Ringler, C. (2024). Levelling the field: A review of the ICT revolution and agricultural extension in the Global South. *Journal of International Development*, 37(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.3949>
- Makinde, O.O., Ogunlade, I, Abidemi, A.O., Shuaib, A.A. & Oladele, O.I. (2025). Knowledge and Attitude of Extension Educators towards Digitising Agricultural Extension Services in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Scientific Journal Warsaw University of Life Sciences*, 25(2), 33-48. DOI: 10.22630/PRS.2025.25.2.7
- Moruppa, S.Y. & Ijabula, S. (2021). Use of Social Media as a Source of Agricultural Information by Farmers in Mubi South Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Engineering Development*, 4(2), 1176-1181.
- Mtega, W. P., Dulle F., Malekani, A. W. & Chailla, A. (2014). The usage of e-resources among agricultural researchers and extension staff in Tanzania. *Library and Information Research*, 38(119), 47-66.
- Mutimba, J. (2024). Agricultural extension debatable issues. *African Journal of Food Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 24(3), 25662-25676. <https://doi.org/10.18697/ajfand.128.24275>
- Nwabugwu, T. S. Nwobodo, C. E. & Okoro, J. C. (2019). Awareness and use of E-Resources among public extension personnel in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 23 (1), 161-170. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jae.v23i1.14>
- Nwaogu, F. K. & Akinbile, L. A (2018). Competencies of agricultural development program personnel in extension service delivery in Oyo and Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 22(3), 40-42.
- Olubiyo, P. O. & Olubiyo, L. M. (2023). Strategies for Preservation of Electronic Information Resources in Academic Libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(3), 50-62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijliss.15/vol9n35062>
- Shehu, D., Ahmed, M. B. & Dewa, A. A. (2023). Essentials of Electronic Information Resources for Information Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in the Contemporary Society. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*, 18(1), 39-45. <https://www.jeweljournals.com>
- Thomas, K. A. & Laseinde, A. A. (2015). Training Needs Assessment on the Use of Social Media among Extension Agents in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Informatics*, 6(1), 100-111.
- Vikas, K. K., Shashidhara, B. S., Reddy, & Goudappa, S. B. (2020). Usage of ICT Tools for Diffusion of Agricultural Information. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 9(7), 3712-3721. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijemas.2020.907.435>
- Yakubu, D. H., Abubakar, B. Z. Atala, T. K. & Muhammed, A. (2013). Use of information and communication technologies among extension agents in Kano State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 17(1), 163-170. <https://journal.aesonnigeria.org/index.php/jae/article/view/88>
- Yarima, F. G. & Saidu, D. (2020). Acquisition and Provision of Access to Electronic Resources: Challenges of Federal University Libraries in the North central State of Nigeria. *Ilorin Varsity International Journal of Library & Information Science*, 3(2), 37-47.